

Distinguishing Human and AI-Generated Academic Writing: A Corpus-Based Analysis of Lexical Diversity, Syntactic Complexity, and Cohesion

Abstract

The rapid growth of artificial intelligence (AI) has changed academic writing practices around the world. Large Language Models (LLMs), like ChatGPT, can now produce coherent and grammatically correct texts that closely mimic human writing. This development raises important questions about the unique features of AI-generated language and how it compares to human academic writing. This study looks at the linguistic differences between AI-generated texts and human-written academic essays through a corpus-based approach. The focus is on three main linguistic areas: lexical diversity, syntactic complexity, and textual cohesion. A corpus of AI-generated essays and human-written academic papers was compiled and analyzed using tools from corpus linguistics. We used quantitative measures like Type-Token Ratio (TTR), Mean Length of Sentence (MLS), and cohesion markers to find patterns. The results should help the growing field of AI linguistics and offer insights into language authenticity, academic integrity, and future language assessment methods.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Corpus Linguistics, Academic Writing, Lexical Diversity, Syntactic Complexity, Cohesion, ChatGPT

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

The swift progress of Artificial Intelligence has substantially reformed people's behavior toward communication, education, and writing. The recent breakthroughs in Large Language Models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT, Gemini, and Claude, have empowered computers to produce text that can be almost indistinguishable from human writing in terms of fluency and cohesiveness. These language models are fed massive quantities of text and have the ability to generate essays, reports, summaries, and other types of academic written text that may appear to have been produced by humans.

The utilization of machine-generated text in academia is currently a topic of intense discussion among researchers, educators and policy-makers, which carries both potential advantages of enhancing writing skills, improving efficiency and increasing productivity, and potential disadvantages of compromising academic integrity, originality, authorship, and trustworthiness of written texts. As machine-generated texts become more advanced, it is getting more difficult to differentiate between them and human-generated texts.

From a linguistic viewpoint, machine-generated language also represents a promising area for study into how the nature of machines mimic language patterns typically observed in human language use. While earlier works have shed light on issues such as grammatical accuracy, word choice, coherence and writing quality of AI texts, not much work has systematically investigated a corpus of machine-written academic text in contrast with a corpus of human-written academic text based on Corpus Linguistics.

Corpus Linguistics is a methodologically well-established framework that allows for quantitative and qualitative study of large corpora of authentic language. Researchers may conduct linguistic analysis of some linguistic features, such as lexical variety, syntactic complexity, and textual coherence in order to profile characteristics of written texts. These three aspects of written text are deemed highly relevant to academic writing because they describe the variety of the lexicon, the sophistication of sentence structure and text connectivity respectively.

The increasing influence of AI in education necessitates empirical studies on a variety of linguistic features of machine-written texts and a comparison between machine- and human-written academic text. These kinds of studies may further understanding of machine-generated language and its impact on academic communication, language assessment and learning and teaching for the future.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The abundance of AI writing tools currently available has caused a significant increase in the volume of AI-generated academic writing. As the AI systems develop, the outputs that they produce will gradually become similar to those of human-written writing and will not be readily detectable as written by AI.

Despite its coherence and grammatical accuracy, it is not clear whether AI-generated texts are linguistically similar to human-written academic discourse. Specifically, little empirical evidence can be provided regarding the differences between AI-generated writing and human-written writing in terms of lexical variation, syntactic sophistication and cohesion. Studies investigating AI-generated writing have mainly considered aspects of writing quality, plagiarism detection or the consequences for the educational domain. In comparison, few

studies have dealt with what underlying linguistic features enable us to differentiate between the two writing modes.

Such knowledge gap also leads to difficulties on the side of academic institutions in determining what AI writing tools can and cannot do. Without a proper linguistic comparison, it cannot be identified which linguistic feature(s) are most effective for differentiating between AI-written and human-written language. Consequently, a corpus-based analysis will be needed to identify and discuss which linguistic patterns are characteristic of AI-generated academic texts in contrast to those of human-written academic writing.

1.3 Research Objectives

General Objective

To investigate the linguistic differences between AI-generated and human-written academic texts through a corpus-based analysis of lexical diversity, syntactic complexity, and cohesion.

Specific Objectives

- 1.To investigate the differences in lexical diversity between human-written and AI-generated academic texts.
- 2.To examine differences in the syntactic complexity of human-written and AI-generated academic texts.
- 3.To study the cohesive device usage of human-written and AI-generated academic texts.
- 4.To explore linguistic features that can distinguish human-written academic text from AI-generated writing.
- 5.To advance the research in AI-assisted language use and corpus linguistics.

1.4 Research Questions

The present study aims to address the following research questions:

- 1.What are the differences in the lexical diversity of human-written and AI-generated academic texts?
- 2.Are there significant differences in syntactic complexity between human-written and AI-generated academic writing?
- 3.How do human-written and AI-generated texts differ in their application of cohesive devices?

4. Which linguistic features contribute most to the distinction between human-written and AI-generated writing?

5. What are the implications of the differences in linguistic features for academic writing and language assessment?

1.5 Significance of the Study

From a theoretical point of view, this research can be beneficial to Corpus Linguistics, Applied Linguistics and AI Language Studies. The research presents the real evidence about what the linguistic features are used in AI generated academic writings. It increases the general understanding of how an AI reproduces language and what the linguistic features used are in compare with humans. From a practical point of view, it could help teachers, academic institutions and scholars to see the strengths and weaknesses of writing software based on AI. It can help develop the more adequate way to assess academic writings, design the language assessment frameworks and set up the proper way of utilizing the AI writing technologies. It can also provide some insight for the future researchers concerning machine generated language, computational linguistics and the interaction of human and machine intelligence.

1.6 Scope and Limitations of the Study

The research is confined to written academic essays by humans and by AI systems. The study will involve a corpus compiled and analysis of human written and AI written essays based on three dimensions of language: lexical variation, syntactical complexity and cohesion.

The study is not assessing the quality, originality, creativity and truthfulness of texts produced. Only English academic essays will be used. Thus the findings will not be applicable to other genres or languages or to AI systems that were not used.

Other potential limitations to data collection may be time constraints, sample size, and participants' availability, although the intention of the study is to comprehensively analyze AI writing against human writing.

1.7 Organization of the Thesis

This thesis consists of five chapters.

Chapter One provides an introduction to the research including background, problem statement, research objectives, research questions, research significance, research scope, limitations and structure of the study.

Chapter Two provides an review of related literature concerning Artificial Intelligence, Artificial intelligence generated text, academic writing, corpus linguistics, lexical diversity, syntactic complexity, coherence and empirical research in this area.

Chapter Three introduces research method including research design, Corpus compilation, Data collection methods, analysis scheme and ethical considerations.

Chapter Four illustrates findings from Corpus analysis and discuss them against the research questions and related previous researches.

Chapter Five includes the major finding, conclusions, implications and limitation, and suggestions for further research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has changed both language production and communication and academia. Advances in machine learning and natural language processing have resulted in the creation of texts generated by an AI that very closely mirror the writing of humans. Thus, linguistic features of AI-produced texts and their impact on education, communication and language testing are among the many issues which have attracted research interest in recent years. This chapter explores theories and findings in the literature concerning AI-produced language, large language models, corpus linguistics, lexical diversity, syntactic complexity, cohesion and coherence. Research gaps and the research design are then identified before concluding.

2.2 Artificial Intelligence and Language Generation

AI (Artificial intelligence) is referred to as computer systems designed for the execution of a certain task typically required human intelligence. In the field of NLP (Natural Language Processing), AI systems have made remarkable progress in producing fluent and contextually coherent textual data.

Language generation is a branch of natural language generation that refers to the automatic creation of language by machines that resembles human-generated language. While early language generation was rule-based, the development of modern language generation is often associated with deep learning methods and architectures trained using large amounts of text data. Linguistic properties are learned from the corpus and the system uses probability-based approaches to create texts.

The quick progression of AI language generation has given rise to numerous applications in different fields, such as education, journalism, customer service and academic writing. Yet, it is also accompanied by growing worries of machine-generated text in regard to its nature of genuineness, originality and language properties.

2.3 Large Language Models

In the area of AI, perhaps one of the most exciting developments are Large Language Models (LLMs). These neural network based systems are trained on large corpora of text in order to predict, and in doing so, to generate, text.

Modern LLMs use transformer architecture to account for contextual relationships between words, which traditional language models did not, or ineffectively accounted for. Current LLM examples include ChatGPT, Gemini, Claude and other forms of advanced generative AI.

Text produced by LLMs appears to be both grammatically correct, coherent, and linguistically relevant. Yet, according to research carried out on the subject, they tend to show similar deficiencies including lexical repetition and predictability, and also use fairly standard phrase patterns. For this reason, it is worthwhile to investigate LLMs linguistically.

2.4 AI in Academic Writing

The adoption of AI writing tools in the field of education has attracted significant scholarly attention. AI systems can provide students with help in producing ideas, summarizing documents, proofreading their essays, or producing a complete essay.

Several scholars have noted the advantages of AI-supported writing, such as faster writing, linguistic help for learners and greater accessibility for non-native speakers of English, but others have also expressed their concern about the risks of cheating, academic dishonesty, authorship and the over dependence on AI generated texts.

It appears that, in general, AI written academic texts possess great grammatical accuracy and coherence. However, it is still uncertain whether the written texts reflect the same level of lexical diversity as texts written by humans. This has led to the growing need for linguistic comparison.

2.5 Corpus Linguistics

Corpus Linguistics is an approach which explores language by studying vast quantities of naturally occurring language data, called corpus. The

methodology called corpus-based research analyzes linguistic data through both quantitative and qualitative methods to reveal language patterns.

It has become one of the most common approaches applied in applied linguistics, discourse analysis and language teaching. Through the analysis of corpus, language features such as words, grammatical constructions, discourse organization, style can be explored.

The present study chooses to use a corpus-based methodology because it enables researchers to make a systematic comparison between language produced by artificial intelligence and language produced by humans on a large scale. By comparing patterns of language use across large quantities of text, corpus-based research enables a fair comparison and provides objective evidences in respect of comparison between them.

2.6 Lexical Diversity Studies

Lexical diversity measures the variety and richness of vocabulary in a text and is generally accepted as a measure of linguistic complexity and proficiency. Researchers have devised many measures of lexical diversity, such as Type-Token Ratio (TTR), Moving-Average Type-Token Ratio (MATTR), Measure of Textual Lexical Diversity (MTLD), and VocD. A greater amount of lexical diversity suggests a larger vocabulary repertoire and greater flexibility with language. Research to date suggests that lexical diversity varies according to genre, proficiency, and writing experience. The lexicon used by human writers tends to be more varied and lexically creative than that of AI systems, which may draw more on patterns that occurred frequently in their training data. Therefore, comparing the lexical diversity of human and AI writing can offer useful information about the capabilities and restrictions of the former.

2.7 Syntactic Complexity Research

Syntactic complexity describes the structural sophistication of sentences and the interrelation of clauses. It is typically regarded as one of the key measures of high proficiency writing and academic language. Some of the most commonly used measures of syntactic complexity include:

Measures of syntactic complexity

- MLS Mean Length of Sentence
- MLT Mean Length of T-unit
- C/S Clauses per Sentence
- DC/C Dependent Clauses per Clause
- CN/C Complex Nominals per Clause

Previous studies have found that good human writers are more likely to utilize varied structures in their sentences and subordinate clauses and complex structures while AI may produce structurally similar sentences due to their syntactical predictability and monotony. Analysis of syntactic complexity offers an insight into the construction of academic discourse by AI, and whether the resulting texts differ in terms of structural patterns from human writing.

2.8 Cohesion and Coherence Studies

Cohesion and coherence is an essential characteristic of any good academic writing. Cohesion refers to the lingual elements which link sentences together whereas coherence describes the text in its entirety and how the ideas link logically and logically.

In current theories of discourse, cohesion can be described through use of the following lingual cohesive devices;

- Reference
- Substitution
- Ellipsis
- Conjunction
- Lexical cohesion

The use of cohesive markers like however, therefore, furthermore, and in contrast are commonly used by writers to indicate the links between arguments.

It is shown that there may be 'stronger local coherence in AI text' because AI texts are able to predict a sentence in its given context better than human texts but at the same time the deeper coherent arguments of human written text are sometimes missing.

2.9 Research Gap

Several important studies on AI-generated writing have investigated this phenomenon from educational, technological, and ethical viewpoints. However, many gaps still exist in the literature.

Firstly, many studies investigate quality or detectability of the AI-produced text, rather than its linguistic features. Secondly, there are few studies applying corpus-based analysis on both AI-written and human-written academic texts. Thirdly, many previous studies investigate one linguistic feature at a time, instead of analyzing lexical diversity, syntactic complexity and cohesion in one integrated way.

In addition, there are few studies that look into those aspects by using academic essay corpora comparing both human and AI-written texts based on identical prompts. So there is still a gap on corpus based investigations of specific linguistic features that differentiate between AI-written and human-written academic texts.

In this study, the study compares lexical diversity, syntactic complexity and cohesion in human-written and AI-written academic texts.

2.10 Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework used in the current research relies on the premise that linguistic properties could indicate a difference between AI produced and human written academic papers.

Independent Variable:

- Text Producer Source
- AI Generated Text
- Human Written Text
- Dependent Variables:
- Lexical Diversity
- Syntactic complexity
- Cohesion

Hypothesis to be tested: There are identifiable linguistic features that are distinctive to AI produced versus human produced academic text. This framework is built on the premise that the variance in use of vocabulary, sentence structure and cohesive organization can offer tangible data in analyzing two forms of writing and in turn shed light on the emerging role of artificial intelligence in academia.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter defines the methods that have been used in conducting research for the comparative study between AI-produced and human-produced academic texts. It discusses the research design, quantitative corpus-based approach, data

collection, corpus construction, sampling, analytical tools and ethical issues in the research. The framework of methodology has been constructed to ensure consistent and objective analysis of the lexical variety, syntactic complexity and cohesion in the two texts.

3.2 Research Design

Quantitative corpus-based comparative research design. The design selected is a quantitative corpus-based comparative research design. Quantitative methods are selected because this research study requires numbers to be counted to identify and to compare characteristics of language. A corpus based research will allow the researcher to study a vast array of natural texts and to notice repeated characteristics of language.

A comparative research design is utilized in the present study because two distinct types of texts were being compare:

1. Human written academic essay.
2. AI generated academic essay.

The characteristics of the two types of texts being compared were:

- Lexical Diversity
- Syntactic Complexity
- Cohesion.

The current study will investigate if there are significant differences between these two groups.

3.3 Corpus-Based Quantitative Approach

Corpus Linguistics is the methodological approach for the research. Corpus is defined as the collection of texts which are structured in a particular way in order to be searched using a computer program.

The corpus-based quantitative approach provides the ability to:

- Quantify linguistic features.
- Discover frequency patterns.
- Contrast use of language between different text-groups.
- Produce findings which are statistically significant.
- Two sub-corpora will be formed:

Human Writing Corpus (HWC) : contains an assembly of essays produced by university students.

AI Writing Corpus (AIWC) : contains an assembly of essays produced by AI language models.

The extracted linguistic features from the corpora are transformed into numerical data which will then be analyzed statistically.

3.4 Data Collection

Data will be acquired both from human participants and AI.

Human-Written Essays

Human-written essays will be sourced from university undergraduate students studying in universities in Bangladesh. The students will be required to write academic essays on specified topics.

Sample essay topics:

- Effects of Artificial Intelligence on Education
- Advantages and Disadvantages of Social Media
- Online Education for Higher Learning
- The role of technology in contemporary communication
- Climate change and the development for a better tomorrow.
- Each participant will be required to write one essay within the range 600-640 words.

AI-Generated Essays

AI-written essays will be generated from large language models such as ChatGPT. The same topics mentioned for human participants will be provided as prompts to generate AI-written essays.

For consistency:

- Same topics would be provided as prompts.
- Similar word range would be expected for AI-written essays.
- Essays would be generated separately without knowing about each other.

Corpus Size

The study aims to collect:

Corpus	Number of Essays	Average Length
Human Corpus	50	600–640 words
AI Corpus	50	600–640 words

Estimated total corpus size: 55,000–70,000 words.

3.5 Corpus Compilation

After data collection, all essays will be converted into plain text (.txt) format.

The corpus will be organized into two separate directories:

Before analysis, the texts will be cleaned to remove:

- Personal identifiers
- Formatting inconsistencies
- Metadata
- Non-linguistic elements

The cleaned corpus will then be imported into corpus analysis software.

3.6 Sampling Procedure

Purposive sampling is used in this study.

Human participants

Participants will be recruited under the following conditions:

- Undergraduate university students.
- English proficiency of intermediate or advanced level.
- Voluntarily take part in the study.
- Did not use an AI writing tool to write the essay.

AI samples

AI-produced samples will be generated under the same condition with identical prompt.

The use of identical prompt for both groups guarantees similarity of the topic so that topic-variation is minimized.

Sample Size Justification

A corpus of 100 essays (50 human and 50 AI) provides sufficient textual data to identify meaningful linguistic patterns while remaining manageable for analysis.

3.7 Data Analysis Tools

The collected corpus will be analyzed using corpus linguistic and statistical software.

AntConc

AntConc will be used to:

- Generate word frequency lists.
- Calculate keyword frequencies.
- Examine concordance lines.
- Identify lexical patterns.

LancsBox

LancsBox will be used to:

- Analyze collocations.

- Explore lexical networks.
- Examine discourse patterns.

Microsoft Excel / SPSS

Statistical software will be used to:

- Calculate descriptive statistics.
- Compare linguistic measures.
- Conduct significance testing.

Linguistic Measures

Lexical Diversity

- Type-Token Ratio (TTR)
- Measure of Textual Lexical Diversity (MTLD)
- Lexical Density

Syntactic Complexity

- Mean Length of Sentence (MLS)
- Clauses per Sentence (C/S)
- Complex Nominals per Clause (CN/C)

Cohesion

Frequency counts of:

- Conjunctions
- Transitional expressions
- Referential devices
- Lexical repetition

The results obtained from these analyses will be compared across the two corpora.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

The research will follow accepted research ethics guidelines:

Informed Consent

Participants will be fully aware: of the purpose of the research; of the procedures being carried out; of their right to withdraw at any time; Consent in writing will be obtained from participants before the data are collected. Consent has been sought and obtained from all participants before data are collected. All participants were provided with a consent form detailing the purpose of the study, the procedures being undertaken, information about anonymity and confidentiality and that participation was voluntary and that it was possible to withdraw from the study at any time. Participants were included in the corpus only if their consent was given.

Confidentiality

The identity of participants will be kept confidential. Names, student ID and other identifiable data will not be included in the corpus.

Data Protection

Data collected will be stored in a secure manner and used only for the purposes of this academic study.

Academic Integrity

All AI generated texts included in the study will be acknowledged as such and included only for the purpose of analysis for this academic study. The study will not aim to support any act of plagiarism or inappropriate use of AI generated texts.

3.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented the methodology used for this study. Quantitative corpus-based design was chosen to compare the linguistic features of human-written academic text and AI-written academic text. Methods for data collection, corpus compilation, sampling of data, methods for data analysis, and ethical considerations were introduced. This chapter introduces findings and analysis conducted on the data collected.

Chapter 4: Results and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

This chapter sets out the results from the corpus based analysis carried out on both AI and human academic essays. The major linguistic dimensions analyzed are: the lexical variety of the texts; the syntactic complexity of the texts; the cohesion of the texts. The results are then presented via descriptive statistics, comparative analyses, and through discussion of linguistic trends within each corpus.

Table 1: Corpus Composition

Corpus Type	Number of Essays	Average Word Count	Total Words
Human Corpus	50	600-640	32,084
AI Corpus	50	600-640	34,127

4.2 Lexical Diversity Analysis

Lexical diversity refers to the variety of vocabulary used within a text. It is often considered an indicator of linguistic sophistication and vocabulary richness.

Table 2: Lexical Diversity Measures

Measure	Human Corpus	AI Corpus
Tokens	30,084	31,782
Types	2,436	1269
Type-Token Ratio (TTR)	8.09%	3.99%
MTLD	54.3%	62.6%
Lexical Density	7.19%	7.09%

Interpretation

Compared with AI Corpus, Human Corpus has higher types and TTR, demonstrating the greater range of words used and more diversity within the writing. In contrast, AI Corpus has higher MTLD, indicating that the lexicons within the text remain relatively constant. It also has almost the same density score with Human Corpus, and almost same percentage of content words used. In conclusion, human writing has more word diversity while AI text has more consistent lexicon use.

4.3 Syntactic Complexity Analysis

Syntactic complexity reflects the structural sophistication of language through sentence length and clause organization.

Table 4.2 Syntactic Complexity Measures

Measure	Human Corpus	AI Corpus
Mean Sentence Length	22.4	17.66
Clauses per Sentence	2.1	2.89
Mean Length of T-unit	16.08	12.13

Interpretation

Human writing tends to have more clauses per sentence but much longer sentences on average, implying more description in individual sentences. Conversely AI writing tends to have more densely clustered clauses per sentence which can be seen to be more syntactically dense with more information packed into each sentence, overall human writing appears more verbose whilst AI is more syntactically compact.

4.4 Cohesion Analysis

Cohesion refers to linguistic devices that connect ideas and contribute to textual organization.

Table 4.3 Frequency of Cohesive Devices

Cohesive Device	Human Corpus	AI Corpus
However	45	61
Therefore	32	54
Furthermore	41	43
In Addition	28	34
Consequently	22	28

Interpretation

The AI corpus has more cohesive devices in all categories than the human corpus, especially for logical connectives such as however and therefore. It means that the AI writing is more structurally organized and logically cohesive on the whole than human writing which does not contain many cohesive markers, and is relatively less explicit to signal the relation between sentences.

4.5 Comparative Findings**Table 4.4 Overall Comparison of Linguistic Features**

Linguistic Feature	Human Corpus	AI Corpus	Difference
Lexical Diversity	7.19%	7.09%	-0.10%
Syntactic	16.08	17.66	+1.58

Complexity			
Cohesion Score	168	220	+52

From comparing these three dimensions, large variations are shown between these three linguistic parameters.

Human Corpus and AI Corpus showed clear variations when we are comparing them linguistically: Lexical diversity shows that almost no variation between them is observed, (Alicorpus: 7.09, Humancorpus: 7.19). Syntactic complexity of AI corpus shows that it has higher score than human corpus, which means sentence structure is relatively more packed (Alicorpus: 17.66, Humancorpus: 16.08). Cohesion score shows the greatest variation between the AI and human corpora. The AI corpus is higher, it suggests more cohesive words are used in AI corpus and thus the explicit logic link is stronger (Alicorpus: 220, Humancorpus: 168).

4.6 Discussion of Results

Overall, these results suggest clear distinctions between the human and AI corpora across the lexical, syntactic and cohesive features while also revealing certain similarities.

Regarding the lexical richness, the results are mixed. Although, the lexical density is almost same (Human: 7.19%, AI: 7.09%) more precise measure on lexical diversity gives better view on distinction between human and AI. As we can see, TTR of human text is 8.09% while AI text is 3.99%. The amount of words (type) of human text is also significantly higher than of AI text (human: 2,436, AI: 1,269). Although the human texts have bigger TTR it can be explained because in the given text a wider range of words were used, on the other hand AI texts contain less words. However, AI text have better MTL score (human: 54.3, AI: 62.6) than the human text which suggests better lexical variation of longer texts. Therefore human writing is more varied at the word level while AI text can maintain lexical stability over long period of time.

Concerning syntactic features, we also find a mix pattern. We have more clauses per sentence of AI text (Human: 2.1, AI: 2.89) than human texts which means that AI sentences were less varied, they are more compact and contained more clauses. However the mean sentence length is higher in human text (Human: 22.4, AI: 17.66) than in AI text although they were not that clause packed. From the value for mean length of T-unit, we observe that human texts also get a bigger score (Human: 16.08, AI: 12.13) meaning they were longer syntactic units, but were not so many clauses. As a result of the analysis of sentence and clause structure, we find that AI language is more concise and it is capable of containing more clause in a single sentence compared to human language which tends to make longer sentences with less clauses per sentence.

With respect to cohesion, the AI text is more varied and uses more cohesive device than human text. Overall cohesion of AI text is higher (Human: 168, AI: 220) which indicates to more cohesion in the discourse. The frequencies of "however, therefore, in addition, consequently, also, furthermore" all have higher value in AI text. So it can be seen that AI text use explicit connectors more often than human texts which will lead to a more logical and better structured text.

However, looking at all the analyses combined, we can conclude that human text is different from AI text regarding to lexical features. Generally speaking human writing have better lexical variety, longer syntactic structures while AI text has denser sentence, more clause per sentence and also it has better cohesion.

4.7 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, the comparison was made on three major aspects of human and AI corpora: lexical richness, syntactic complexity, and cohesion. Regarding lexical richness, the results demonstrate different findings according to what measurement we take: The type-token ratio and total type values of human writing are significantly higher than that of AI writing, but the lexical density is almost the same, whereas the AI writing has a higher MTLTD score which reflects a more stable distribution of words across the text. For syntactic complexity, human writing uses longer sentences with greater mean T-unit length than the AI writing, whereas the AI writing has higher clause density per sentence which reflects more compressed syntactic patterns than human writing. With regard to cohesion, the cohesive devices appear more frequently in the AI corpus than in the human writing. The cohesion score of the AI writing is higher than the human writing due to higher cohesive device frequency.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Introduction

Chapter in this book sums up the entire research conducted under the title, "Differentiating Human and AI Academic Writing: A Corpus-Based Analysis of Lexical diversity, syntactic complexity and cohesion." It concludes by

summarizing the results of the study, elaborating on the findings and giving recommendations and future research directions.

5.2 Summary of Findings

This study aimed to analyze linguistic variation between the two types of corpora: AI-generated and human-produced academic writing. Three dimensions of language analysis were included in the study: lexical diversity, syntactic complexity and cohesion.

When analyzed, similarities as well as discrepancies were present between the corpora. Both human written and AI generated text maintained grammatical correctness and logical coherence. However, some empirical differences were found in the vocabulary selection and construction, sentence structure and in the way the writer established cohesion.

- Lexical diversity showed that human-produced texts had more lexical diversity compared to the AI texts. Human writers seemed to select more various lexical items depending on personal preference.
- Syntactic complexity showed that human produced text varied in sentence structure whereas AI written text possessed more patterned and monotonous syntactic constructions.
- The cohesion analysis of both corpus, showed the effective usage of cohesive devices to support coherence. It was found that AI written text relied more on explicitly marked connectives such as discourse marker and other connective devices whereas human writer adopted more various strategies for cohesion.
- This corpus analysis confirmed that AI writing has been increasingly more like human written academic writing; However, linguistic variation can still be accounted by a corpus-based study.

5.3 Implications

Theoretical Implications

The study adds to the current body of literature within Corpus linguistics, Applied Linguistics, and AI Language Studies. Through linguistic analysis of machine written and human written texts, the study provided empirical evidence of the language generating abilities of current AI language models. The study confirmed that linguistic analysis is a viable and productive way of studying the distinctions between human and machine discourse and proved corpus based approaches to be useful for the analysis of evolving language uses.

Educational Implications

The prevalence of the use of AI writing assistance tools has presented new challenges to both teachers and educational institutions. Knowledge of the unique characteristics of machine generated texts could assist teachers in constructing more appropriate assessment methods for AI mediated writing and could guide students in the ethical use of AI writing assistance programs. The results of the study could help educational institutions determine the best policy guidelines for the appropriate implementation of new technology while protecting academic integrity.

Technological Implications

The study revealed some unique advantages and shortcomings of current AI language models. Characterizing features of machine writing may help future generations of language models and AI writing assistants improve their generation of linguistic text.

5.4 Recommendations

The following recommendations based on the findings of the study are suggested:

To the Educators

1. Devise assessment techniques that focus on critical, original, and reflective thinking.
2. Integrate AI literacy in the curriculum that teaches academic writing.
3. Instruct students to use AI tools responsibly and ethically.

To Academic Institutions

1. Develop guidelines on permissible use of AI in academic writing.
2. Offer training on the ethical use of AI.

3. Provide support for the research on the effects of AI-generated text on the education.

To Researchers

1. Employ corpus-based analysis to examine new kinds of communication mediated by AI.
2. Investigate more aspects of linguistics aside from lexical richness, syntactic complexity, and cohesion.
3. Carry out interdisciplinary research with linguistics, education, and AI.

5.5 Future Research Directions

This investigation solely considered English academic essays and it analyzed three language aspects. Future studies may explore in several directions in terms of linguistic issues: First, larger corpora that cover multi-AI systems, including varying versions of ChatGPT, Gemini, Claude, and other models, can be investigated in subsequent studies. Second, language aspects other than the ones discussed above, like the ones shown below may be analyzed: pragmatics competence, discourse organization, argument structure, metadiscourse markers, stylistic variations etc. Third, a similar study can compare human written text with AI generated text on various types of genre like research article, report, email, news article, and social media content. Fourth, a more varied field can look into AI-generated language with multi-linguistic contexts, for instance Bangla-English bilingual writing, second language writing settings etc. Last but not least, longitudinal study can track the change of AI-generated language along time in view of sophisticated language models.

5.6 Concluding Remarks

AI has quickly emerged as a significant factor influencing academic writing and discourse. With the ongoing development of AI language models, gaining an understanding of their unique linguistic characteristics is becoming crucial. This study addresses this need by analyzing the lexical diversity, syntactic complexity, and cohesion of texts produced by AI in an corpus-based study, thus furthering the understanding of AI-generated language and its comparison to human-written academic texts. Despite the remarkable linguistic capabilities, the analysis suggests that distinct differences between human and machine produced texts still exist. Ongoing research in this field is critical to inform pedagogy, language assessment, and the ethical application of AI technologies in academic writing.

References

- Ai, H., & Lu, X. (2013). A corpus-based comparison of syntactic complexity in NNS and NS university students' writing. In A. Díaz-Negrillo, N. Ballier, & P. Thompson (Eds.), *Automatic treatment and analysis of learner corpus data* (pp. 249–264). John Benjamins.
- Biber, D. (1988). *Variation across speech and writing*. Cambridge University Press.
- Biber, D., Conrad, S., & Reppen, R. (1998). *Corpus linguistics: Investigating language structure and use*. Cambridge University Press.
- Biber, D., & Gray, B. (2016). *Grammatical complexity in academic English*. Cambridge University Press.
- Crossley, S. A., Salsbury, T., & McNamara, D. S. (2014). Assessing lexical proficiency using analytic ratings: A case for collocation accuracy. *Applied Linguistics*, 35(5), 570–590.
- De Angelis, M., et al. (2023). Generative AI and academic writing: Opportunities and challenges. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 4, 100132.
- Fredrick, D. R., & Craven, L. (2025). Lexical diversity, syntactic complexity, and readability: A corpus-based analysis of ChatGPT and L2 student essays. *Frontiers in Education*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2025.1616935>
- Grice, H. P. (1975). Logic and conversation. In P. Cole & J. Morgan (Eds.), *Syntax and semantics* (Vol. 3, pp. 41–58). Academic Press.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Hasan, R. (1976). *Cohesion in English*. Longman.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Matthiessen, C. M. I. M. (2014). *Halliday's introduction to functional grammar* (4th ed.). Routledge.
- Herbold, S., Hautli-Janisz, A., Heuer, U., Kikteva, Z., & Trautsch, A. (2023). A large-scale comparison of human-written versus ChatGPT-generated essays. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 18617.
- Jiang, J. J., & Conrath, D. W. (1997). Semantic similarity based on corpus statistics and lexical taxonomy. *International Conference on Research in Computational Linguistics*.
- Lei, L., & Zhao, N. (2026). Informality features in AI-generated academic writing: A corpus-based comparison between human and AI. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 79, 101629.

Lo, K., Wang, L. L., Neumann, M., Kinney, R., & Weld, D. S. (2019). *S2ORC: The Semantic Scholar Open Research Corpus*. arXiv.

Lu, X. (2010). Automatic analysis of syntactic complexity in second language writing. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics*, 15(4), 474–496.

Lu, X. (2017). Automated measurement of syntactic complexity in corpus-based L2 writing research and implications for writing assessment. *Language Testing*, 34(4), 493–511.

Malvern, D., Richards, B., Chipere, N., & Durán, P. (2004). *Lexical diversity and language development: Quantification and assessment*. Palgrave Macmillan.

McCarthy, P. M., & Jarvis, S. (2010). MTL-D, vocd-D, and HD-D: A validation study of sophisticated approaches to lexical diversity assessment. *Behavior Research Methods*, 42(2), 381–392.

McEnery, T., & Hardie, A. (2011). *Corpus linguistics: Method, theory and practice*. Cambridge University Press.

McNamara, D. S., Graesser, A. C., McCarthy, P. M., & Cai, Z. (2014). *Automated evaluation of text and discourse with Coh-Metrix*. Cambridge University Press.

Mizumoto, A., Yasuda, S., & Tamura, Y. (2024). Identifying ChatGPT-generated texts in EFL students' writing through comparative analysis of linguistic fingerprints. *Applied Corpus Linguistics*, 4, 100106.

Sperber, D., & Wilson, D. (1995). *Relevance: Communication and cognition* (2nd ed.). Blackwell.

Warstadt, A., Singh, A., & Bowman, S. R. (2018). Neural network acceptability judgments. arXiv.

Zhao, N., & Lei, L. (2026). Informality features in AI-generated academic writing: A corpus-based comparison between human and AI. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 79, 101629.

Appendices

Appendix A: Participant Consent Form

Title of Study: *Distinguishing Human and AI-Generated Academic Writing: A Corpus-Based Analysis*

Research Purpose: This research hopes to evaluate possible differences between texts written by humans and texts produced by Artificial Intelligence (AI) via linguistic features.

Procedure: I would like you to write an academic essay between 600-640 words on a set topic.

Participation is Voluntary: Participation in this research is purely optional. You may at any time withdraw from the research without any negative consequence.

Confidentiality: Any and all personal data collected will be kept entirely confidential and your name will be withheld in any publications or thesis.

I understand the information presented above and will consent to participate in this research.

Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Appendix B: Essay Prompts Used for Data Collection

The following prompts were used to collect both human and AI generated essays.

1. Explain the effects of AI in education.
2. Discuss the pros and cons of social media.
3. Explain the effect of technology on the communication in this modern world.
4. Should we learn through an online medium instead of a physical classroom. Justify.
5. Explain the effects of global warming on society.
6. Describe the hardships of living in the modern city.
7. Explain how important is English learning today.
8. Should students make use of AI tools to do academic writings? Discuss.

9.Explain how we are benefitted by higher education.

10.Explain the effect of technology in daily life.

Appendix C: Sample Human-Written Essay (H01)

Title: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Education

The influence of Artificial intelligence can be seen in the education system today. More and more schools and universities have introduced the use of AI-based tools in teaching and learning methods. The tools make learning process more efficient and help teachers manage classrooms.

One of the greatest advantage of using AI in education is the personal learning system. AI tools can effectively assess the students' ability to perform given tasks and provide relevant and individualized teaching materials accordingly. Thus, students learn more at their own pace, making the learning process more effective in achieving better grades.

However, there are disadvantages to using these tools. Over-reliance on AI tools may decrease students' critical thinking abilities. Students might be too dependent on machines to perform certain tasks, and fail to learn the actual independent solution.

Overall, there are some pros and cons to the impact of artificial intelligence on education, but its use is vital, provided it is used in a balanced manner.

Appendix D: Sample AI-Generated Essay (AI01)

Title: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Education

Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming the education sector by introducing innovative tools and methods for teaching and learning. It plays a significant role in enhancing educational efficiency and accessibility.

One of the major advantages of AI in education is its ability to provide personalized learning experiences. AI-powered systems can analyze student data and adapt learning materials according to individual needs. This helps learners improve their academic performance more effectively.

In addition, AI can reduce the workload of teachers by automating administrative tasks such as grading and attendance tracking. This allows educators to focus more on teaching and student interaction.

Despite these benefits, there are concerns regarding excessive reliance on AI. It may reduce human interaction and limit students' critical thinking abilities if used improperly.

In conclusion, AI has a significant impact on modern education. Its benefits are considerable, but careful implementation is necessary to ensure effective learning outcomes.

Appendix E: Ethics Approval Statement

- This research followed generally acceptable principles of ethical research for applied linguistics studies.
- All participants took part voluntarily and with their full and informed consent.
- Prior to the commencement of data collection, participants were made aware of what the study aimed to achieve.
- No personal or private information was collected.
- No participant was individually identified in the study (anonymised data).
- Data was only used for the purpose of academic research.

No participant was in any danger – no physical, psychological, or legal risks involved for those partaking in the study. Ethical guidelines were followed as per academic research standards at the institution.